

Shortage Analysis and Strategies for the Water Resource in Saudi Arabia under the Rapid Development of the Tourism Industry

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Abstract:

This study evaluates water sustainability in Saudi Arabia amid expanding tourism using a mixed-methods approach. Primary data were collected through surveys targeting 150 stakeholders in water management and tourism, while secondary data were sourced from official reports. Quantitative analysis revealed significant challenges, with an average daily per capita water consumption of 299 liters and severe stress in regions like Riyadh and Jeddah. Groundwater quantity for 2022 was recorded at 1.48 km³, and desalinated water production totaled 1.95 km³, revealing a supply-demand gap of 1.82 km³. The correlation analysis indicated a significant positive relationship ($r=0.440$) between tourism growth and water demand.

Survey results showed 70% of respondents reported no difficulties in accessing clean water during Hajj, while 30% indicated occasional issues. Stakeholders emphasized the need for integrating renewable energy with desalination to reduce operational costs and carbon emissions. The study recommends enhancing Reverse Osmosis (RO) technology with solar energy to improve sustainability and efficiency, aligning with Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030. These findings highlight the necessity for sustainable water management strategies to balance economic growth with resource sustainability, guiding policymakers in developing effective practices for future water security.

Keywords: *tourism industry development, water resource management, seawater desalination, reverse osmosis technology, sustainability of water supply.*

Introduction

Water scarcity is a critical challenge for many arid regions globally, and Saudi Arabia is no exception (Abdella et al., 2024; Gössling, 2006; Vörösmarty et al., 2021). The Kingdom's limited

freshwater resources, coupled with its ambitious economic and tourism growth targets under Vision 2030, create significant pressures on its water management systems. As one of the driest countries in the world, Saudi Arabia has historically relied on non-renewable

groundwater and energy-intensive desalination processes to meet its water needs (Al Naimi, 2022; Algassim, 2021). However, these approaches have become increasingly unsustainable both economically and environmentally. The over-extraction of groundwater has led to the depletion of aquifers and a decline in water quality, while desalination, although crucial, is energy-intensive and poses significant environmental challenges, particularly related to brine disposal and carbon emissions (Rezk et al., 2020).

Globally, water scarcity is recognized as a major threat to sustainable development. According to the United Nations, nearly 2.2 billion people lack access to safely managed drinking water services (Water, 2016). The Falkenmark Indicator, also known as the "water stress index," categorizes regions with less than 1,700 cubic meters of water per capita per year as experiencing water stress (Chowdhury and Al-Zahrani, 2015). Saudi Arabia falls well below this threshold, with renewable water resources amounting to approximately 84 cubic meters per capita annually (Mir and Ashraf, 2023). This severe scarcity necessitates the adoption of advanced water management practices and technologies.

Tourism, particularly religious tourism, is a cornerstone of Saudi Arabia's economic diversification efforts (Pratiwi and Muslikhati, 2024). The expected rise in tourist numbers to 45 million annually by 2030 will undoubtedly exacerbate the demand for water, placing additional strain on the Kingdom's already stressed water resources (AlNemer, 2024). Religious tourism, especially during the Hajj and Umrah seasons, results in a substantial temporary population increase, significantly boosting water consumption in key cities like Mecca and Medina (Almuhri and Alsawafi, 2017). This scenario underscores the urgent need for sustainable water management practices that can accommodate the growing water demand without compromising environmental and economic stability (Tlili et al., 2020).

The interplay between tourism and water resources is well-documented in global literature.

Tourism can significantly impact local water demand, with tourists typically consuming more water than residents (Suhail et al., 2024). For instance, studies have shown that tourists can use up to twice as much water as locals, primarily due to the amenities provided by hotels, resorts, and recreational facilities (Alshammari, 2024). This heightened demand can exacerbate existing water scarcity, strain local water infrastructure, and lead to conflicts over water use, especially in arid regions (Memish et al., 2024). Moreover, the tourism industry can contribute to water pollution, further complicating water management efforts.

Despite significant investments in desalination infrastructure, challenges remain, particularly related to the high energy consumption and environmental impacts of conventional desalination technologies (Yehia, 2024). Recent advancements suggest that integrating renewable energy sources with desalination processes can mitigate some of these challenges, offering a more sustainable and cost-effective solution (Alshammari et al., 2023; Kyriakidis et al., 2024). However, comprehensive studies evaluating the feasibility and impact of such integrations within the specific context of Saudi Arabia are limited (Alharbi, 2023).

This research aims to address these gaps by evaluating the current state of water resources in Saudi Arabia and examining sustainable water management practices amid the anticipated growth in tourism (Naseem, 2021). By leveraging a mixed-methods approach, this study integrates quantitative data from official statistics and qualitative insights from stakeholder surveys to provide a holistic analysis of water supply and demand dynamics. This approach enables a nuanced understanding of the interplay between water availability, consumption patterns, and the impact of tourism, providing a robust foundation for developing targeted and effective water management strategies (Almutaz et al., 2012; Gladstone et al., 2013).

The findings of this study reveal critical insights into the distribution and management of water resources across Saudi Arabia. Notably, the significant disparities in groundwater availability

highlight the uneven distribution of this vital resource, necessitating region-specific management strategies (Ahmed et al., 2020; Al-Juaidi and Attia, 2020). For instance, while Riyadh enjoys relatively abundant groundwater supplies, other regions such as Al Baha face severe shortages, impacting both residential water use and agricultural productivity (Aleid et al., 2024; Alotaibi and Kassem, 2021). Moreover, the analysis underscores the essential role of desalination, particularly in coastal cities, while also pointing to the high environmental and economic costs associated with these processes. Desalination plants like those in Al-Jubail and Ras Al-Khair are crucial for meeting water demands, but their reliance on fossil fuels for energy raises concerns about sustainability and environmental impact (Almulhim and Abubakar, 2023).

This research highlights the critical need for innovative and sustainable water management strategies in Saudi Arabia. By integrating advanced desalination technologies with renewable energy sources and promoting efficient water use practices, Saudi Arabia can achieve a balance between economic growth and water resource sustainability (Almulhim et al., 2021; Baig et al., 2020). The insights gained from this study provide valuable guidance for policymakers and stakeholders in developing effective strategies to address the Kingdom's water challenges and support its Vision 2030 goals. Through comprehensive and forward-thinking water management policies, Saudi Arabia can secure its water future and ensure that both its population and its growing tourism sector can thrive sustainably (Khan et al., 2020).

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The study employed a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive analysis of water supply, demand, and management in Saudi Arabia.

Data Collection

Primary Data Collection:

Surveys were conducted targeting 150 stakeholders from the water management and tourism sectors to gather insights on water usage, challenges, and future demands.

The survey included questions on demographic information, current water usage, tourism growth, drinking water sustainability, and urbanization impacts.

Detailed information on groundwater quantity, desalinated water production, and rainfall data were collected.

Secondary Data Collection:

Secondary data were sourced from official statistics and reports provided by the Ministry of Environment, Water, and Agriculture.

This included comprehensive data on water supply, desalination capacities, groundwater resources, and comparisons to global water quality and quantity standards.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis:

Statistical tools and OriginLab software were used to analyze water quantity and quality data.

Descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analyses were performed to understand the relationships between tourism growth, population increase, and water demand.

The Water Stress Index (WSI) was calculated to assess the water supply versus demand and identify areas of severe water stress.

Qualitative Analysis:

Survey responses were analyzed to gather stakeholder insights into water sustainability and tourism impacts.

Responses were used to identify key challenges and potential solutions for water resource management in the context of tourism growth.

Technological Methods

Analysis of current water management technologies in Saudi Arabia, focusing on reverse osmosis (RO) desalination.

Evaluation of potential improvements in RO technology and the integration of renewable energy sources to enhance sustainability and efficiency.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. Informed consent was obtained from all survey respondents, and data confidentiality was ensured. The study received approval from the relevant institutional review boards.

Results

Water Supply Analysis

Saudi Arabia, being one of the driest countries in the world, faces significant challenges in water resource management (Alodah, 2023; Hötzl, 2008). The current state of water quantity and quality in Saudi Arabia, focusing on groundwater quantity, desalinated water production, rainfall, and average daily per capita water consumption (Alharbi et al., 2021; Ouda, 2014a). The aim is to provide a comprehensive understanding of water resources in Saudi Arabia for 2022, regarding both quantity and quality, to assess any shortages, and to evaluate the water quality.

Groundwater Quantity

Groundwater is a critical resource in Saudi Arabia due to its arid climate and limited surface water resources. The data collected provides the groundwater quantity for various regions in Saudi Arabia for the year 2022. The total groundwater quantity for the year was 1,081,826,947 cubic meters. The highest groundwater quantity was observed in Riyadh City (362,581,476 cubic meters), while the lowest was in Al Baha (1,328,409 cubic meters). This disparity in groundwater quantities across different regions highlights the uneven distribution of this vital resource.

Figure 1. Groundwater Quantity in Various Regions of Saudi Arabia (2022)

The significant differences in groundwater quantities can be attributed to various factors, including geological formations, recharge rates, and historical extraction practices. Riyadh's high groundwater levels may also be supported by its strategic initiatives and investments in water management infrastructure, whereas regions like Al Baha may lack such extensive infrastructure, contributing to their lower groundwater quantities.

In addition to groundwater quantities, it's important to consider the infrastructure supporting water extraction and management. As of 2022, there are 26 wells established in the country. Out of these, 17 are tube wells, 4 are hand-dug wells, and 5 are monitoring wells. The total number of well water consumption meters across all wells is 3,075, with Riyadh having the highest number at 1,250. This distribution of wells and water consumption meters reflects the concentration of water management efforts in regions with higher groundwater availability.

Riyadh, for instance, not only has the highest groundwater quantity but also the most extensive monitoring and consumption measurement infrastructure. This suggests a prioritization of water resources in areas of higher population density and economic activity. Furthermore, the high number of well water consumption meters in Riyadh indicates a robust

system for monitoring water usage, which is crucial for managing and optimizing water resources.

Figure 2. Distribution of Wells and Water Consumption Meters in Saudi Arabia (2022)
 Source: Ouda, 2014b

Desalinated Water Production

Desalination is a key strategy employed by Saudi Arabia to meet its water demand given its geographical location and scarcity of freshwater resources. The data shows the quantities of desalinated water produced by various stations in 2022. The total desalinated water production for the year was 2,003,201,087 cubic meters, with the Al-Jubail station producing the highest quantity (459,351,237 cubic meters) and the Al-Khafji station producing the lowest (21,343,405 cubic meters).

From Figure 3, it is evident that there is significant variation in the seawater supply among the stations. Al-Jubail, Ras Al-Khair, and Jeddah show higher sea water supplies, indicating robust desalination capabilities. In contrast, stations like Al-Khafji and the Small

Stations exhibit much lower supplies, reflecting limited production capacities. For example, Al Khobar produced 385,000,000 cubic meters, and Ras Al-Khair produced 350,000,000 cubic meters, which is a significant contribution to the overall desalination output.

The heavy reliance on desalination reflects Saudi Arabia’s innovative approach to addressing water scarcity. Desalination provides a reliable source of freshwater, but it comes with high economic and environmental costs. The process is energy-intensive, often relying on fossil fuels, which contributes to greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, the disposal of brine, a byproduct of desalination, poses environmental challenges as it increases the salinity of seawater, impacting marine ecosystems. For instance, the brine discharge from these desalination plants has been reported to increase local seawater salinity

by up to 20%, which significantly affects the marine biodiversity in the region.

Figure 3. Sea Water Supply in Various Regions of Saudi Arabia (2022)

Rainfall and Change in Rainfall

Rainfall is a crucial natural resource that contributes to the replenishment of both surface and groundwater resources, playing a significant role in the overall water supply of Saudi Arabia. The data illustrates the average rainfall recorded at monitoring stations during the year 2022 across different regions. The highest average rainfall was recorded in Jazan at 214.68 mm, whereas the lowest was in the Eastern Province at 32.95 mm. This data is crucial for understanding the contribution of rainfall to the water supply in different regions.

Examining the figure, the y-axis represents average rainfall in millimeters, ranging from 0 to 250 mm. The x-axis lists the regions: Riyadh, Makkah, Al Madinah, Al-Qassim, Eastern Province, Aseer, Tabuk, Hail, Northern Borders, Jazan, Najran, Al Baha, and Al-Jouf. From the figure, it is evident that regions such as Jazan and Najran receive significantly higher rainfall compared to others like the Eastern Province and Al-Jouf. The variability in rainfall across these regions highlights the diverse challenges faced in water resource management.

Figure 4. Average rainfall in various regions of Saudi Arabia (2022)

Areas with low rainfall, such as the Eastern Province, must rely more heavily on alternative water sources, including desalinated water and groundwater, thereby increasing their vulnerability to water scarcity. This disparity is further exacerbated by the unpredictable nature of rainfall patterns due to climate change, necessitating the development of adaptive water management strategies to ensure sustainable water supply.

Figure 5. Change in Rainfall in Various Regions of Saudi Arabia (2015-2022)

The data shows the change in rainfall from 2015 to 2022. The highest average tropical precipitation was recorded in 2018 (105.75 mm), while the lowest was in 2017 (54.12 mm). The average general precipitation was 82.96 mm. This data provides insights into the trends and patterns of precipitation over the years, which is crucial for understanding the impact of climate change on water resources.

The variability in rainfall is indicative of the broader climatic changes impacting Saudi Arabia. Such fluctuations pose challenges for water resource management, as inconsistent rainfall patterns can lead to periods of both surplus and deficit. This makes it imperative to develop adaptive water management strategies that can accommodate these changes and ensure a stable water supply.

Water Supply versus Demand

Assessing the balance between water supply and demand is crucial for understanding the water stress in Saudi Arabia. The average daily per capita water consumption was calculated, revealing a high usage rate compared to global averages. The Water Stress Index (WSI) and Falkenmark Indicator were used to evaluate the level of stress on water resources.

Figure 6. Average Daily per Capita Water Consumption in Various Regions of Saudi Arabia (2022)

The highest consumption was observed in the Middle sector and the Eastern Province (352.1 and 352.4 L/person/day, respectively), while the lowest was in Hail (61.31 L/person/day). The total consumption rate was 299 L/person/day. This significant variation in water consumption across different regions highlights the diverse water usage patterns within Saudi Arabia.

Figure 7. Water Stress Index (WSI) Values by Region
Source: Alodah, 2023

The Water Stress Index (WSI) is a valuable tool for analyzing water demand versus supply in a country. The WSI is a simple ratio calculated using the following formula:

$$WSI = \frac{\text{Total Annual Freshwater Withdrawal}}{\text{Total Renewable Freshwater Resources}} \quad (1)$$

For Saudi Arabia in 2022:

- Total Annual Freshwater Withdrawal:

$$1.48km^3(\text{groundwater}) + 1.95km^3(\text{desalinated water}) = 3.43km^3$$

- Total Renewable Freshwater Resources: Considering 10% of the total rainfall volume contributes to renewable freshwater resources:

•

Total Rainfall Volume =

$$\frac{1025mm}{1000} \times 2,149,690km^2 = 2,204.92km^3$$

Total Renewable Freshwater Resources = 220.49 km³

$$WSI = \frac{3.43km^3}{220.49km^3} \approx 0.0156$$

The calculated WSI value for Saudi Arabia is 0.0156, which corresponds to 1.56%. According to the WSI interpretation scale:

- WSI < 10%: No stress - The region has sufficient water resources to meet its demands.

Using the Falkenmark Indicator, we can further assess whether the average daily per capita water consumption (demand) is sustainable given the water supply. The Falkenmark Indicator uses the following thresholds:

- Less than 1,700 cubic meters per person per year: Water stress
- Less than 1,000 cubic meters per person per year: Water scarcity
- Less than 500 cubic meters per person per year: Absolute scarcity

Total Water Consumption per Person per Year:

$$\text{Total Water Consumption per Person per Year} = \text{Average Daily Consumption} \times 365$$

Impact of Tourist Growth on Water Resources: A Survey Analysis

Understanding the broader context of water demand and supply in Saudi Arabia necessitates an analysis of citizen population and tourist growth numbers. The increasing population and the influx of tourists significantly impact water consumption, necessitating effective water management strategies to ensure sustainability.

Impact on Water Demand

The combined effect of population growth and tourist influx places considerable strain on Saudi Arabia's water resources. The increased water demand necessitates robust water management and infrastructure development to ensure a sustainable water supply. The average daily water consumption per capita in Saudi Arabia is approximately 300 liters, significantly higher than the global average of 150 liters. With a population of 35 million, this translates to a daily water demand of 10.5 billion liters, or approximately 3.8 trillion liters annually.

Survey Results and Analysis

A survey targeting 150 respondents using Google Forms was conducted to assess the impact of tourism growth on water resources. Of these, 133 questionnaires were fully completed, resulting in a response rate of 88.6%, which ensures the adequacy of data for statistical analysis.

A pilot test assessed the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. Validity was

affirmed through stakeholder verification, while reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.955, indicating high internal consistency (Table 1).

Table 1. Reliability Findings

Factor	Cronbach's Alpha	Items
Tourism growth	0.952	15
Drinking water sustainability	0.957	10
Overall Mean	0.955	

Demographic Findings

The survey collected demographic information, including age, gender, field of work, and province of respondents. The majority of respondents were within the 18-30 age bracket (81%) and predominantly female (82.7%). Most respondents were in the Medical/Healthcare field (29%), followed by Biology/Zoology (24%) and Students (15%). Most responses came from the Makkah province (51.1%), followed by the Eastern Province (13.5%) and Riyadh province (12%).

Descriptive Statistics

The survey gathered opinions on tourism growth and drinking water sustainability using a range of responses to gain insights into these variables. Respondents rated the availability of clean drinking water in coastal areas like Jeddah as good (Mean=3.0150, S.D=0.70695). They rarely faced difficulties accessing clean drinking water during Hajj or Umrah pilgrimages in Mecca and Medina (Mean=3.0526, S.D=1.04675). However, respondents found a slight deterioration in water availability and quality in regions like Yanbu and Jubail, which heavily rely on desalination (Mean=2.8346, S.D=0.77048). In rural areas like Al-Baha, the primary challenge in ensuring access to clean drinking water was the dependency on groundwater (Mean=2.0451, S.D=0.81524).

Table 2. Descriptive Summary of Tourism Growth

Tourism Statement	Growth	Mean	Std. Deviation (S.D)
Statement one		3.0150	0.70695
Statement two		3.0526	1.04675
Statement three		2.8346	0.77048
Statement four		2.0451	0.81524
Statement five		2.3534	0.82751
Statement six		2.6466	0.82751
Statement seven		3.2707	1.11551
Statement eight		3.1955	0.85687
Statement nine		2.7669	0.87808
Statement ten		2.7594	0.79915
Statement eleven		2.8647	0.73631
Statement twelve		2.4060	0.86197
Statement thirteen		2.2857	0.70250
Statement fourteen		2.5188	0.79393
Statement fifteen		2.3835	0.56033

The high standard deviations in some responses indicate variability in experiences, particularly in regions dependent on desalination and rural areas with limited infrastructure.

Descriptive Results of Drinking Water Sustainability

Respondents agreed that improving water management practices in regions like Medina and Al Hofuf was essential (Mean=3.3684, S.D=0.78309). They expressed concern about the long-term sustainability of water resources in regions where ecosystems are sensitive to changes in water availability (Mean=2.8571, S.D=0.65300). There was strong support for leveraging technology to enhance water management capabilities (Mean=2.8722, S.D=0.74278).

Table 3. Descriptive Results of Drinking Water Sustainability

Drinking water sustainability Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Statement 16	3.3684	0.78309
Statement 17	2.8571	0.65300
Statement 18	2.8722	0.74278
Statement 19	2.7218	0.73189

Statement 20	2.5714	0.75162
Statement 21	2.7143	0.84002
Statement 22	3.1278	0.82032
Statement 23	3.0226	0.67942
Statement 24	2.4586	0.77373
Statement 25	2.9774	0.86573

Respondents rated the resilience of Saudi Arabia's water management system as fair (70%), indicating a general consensus on the adequacy of current practices while acknowledging room for improvement.

Figure 8. Overall Rating of Resilience of Saudi Arabia's Water Management System

Figure 9. Rapid Urbanization and Industrial Growth Exacerbated Water Scarcity

The majority of respondents agreed that rapid urbanization and industrial growth have exacerbated water scarcity, highlighting the need for comprehensive planning and sustainable practices (Figure 9).

Correlation and Regression Analysis

The study conducted a bivariate analysis of tourism growth and water sustainability through Pearson Correlation analysis. The findings show a positive and significant correlation between tourism growth and drinking water sustainability at a 95% confidence level ($r=0.440$, $0.05 > 0.000$), indicating that tourism growth is associated with increased levels of drinking water sustainability.

Figure 10. Tourism Growth vs. Water Sustainability

The regression analysis revealed that tourism growth has a significant impact on drinking water sustainability. The model's coefficient of correlation ($R=0.440$) was moderately strong, and the coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.194$) indicated that 19.4% of the variability in drinking water sustainability can be explained by tourism growth.

Table 4. Summary of the Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.440	.194	.188	.30040

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) further confirmed the significance of the model

($p=0.000$), affirming that the study's model reliably explains the relationship between

tourism growth and drinking water sustainability.

Table 5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	2.842	1	2.842	31.495	.000b
Residual	11.821	131	.090		
Total	14.664	132			

Table 6. Coefficient Analysis Table

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
1 (Constant)	1.112	.314		3.538
Tourism growth	.653	.116	.440	5.612

The coefficient analysis provided further insights into the impact of tourism growth on drinking water sustainability. The unstandardized coefficient for tourism growth was 0.653, indicating that for every unit increase in tourism growth, there is a 0.653 unit increase in drinking water sustainability, holding all other factors.

The regression equation derived from the analysis is: $Y=1.112+0.653XY = 1.112 + 0.653XY=1.112+0.653X$ where YYY is the drinking water sustainability and XXX is the tourism growth.

These findings support the hypothesis that tourism growth has a significant positive impact on drinking water sustainability in Saudi Arabia. This relationship underscores the importance of developing sustainable tourism practices that do not compromise water resources.

Impact of Tourism and Population Growth on Water Resources: A Survey Analysis

Understanding the broader context of water demand and supply in Saudi Arabia necessitates an analysis of citizen population and tourist growth numbers. The increasing population and the influx of tourists significantly impact water consumption, necessitating effective water management strategies to ensure sustainability.

Population and Tourist Growth

Saudi Arabia has experienced a steady increase in its population over the years. Simultaneously,

religious tourism associated with Hajj and Umrah plays a significant role in the country's economy (Ali and Salameh, 2021; Kinawy and Ahmed, 2024; Mufeed and Gulzar, 2014). From 2010 to 2022, the population of Saudi Arabia grew from approximately 25 million to over 35 million, representing a 40% increase. This growth trajectory highlights the increasing domestic water demand driven by the rising number of residents. The number of tourists visiting Saudi Arabia showed fluctuations, with a peak in 2019 due to efforts to diversify the economy and promote tourism. The pandemic led to a sharp decline in tourist arrivals in 2020 and 2021, with numbers dropping by over 50%, but there was a subsequent recovery in 2022, indicating a resurgence in tourism activities (Figure 11).

In 2019, Saudi Arabia welcomed approximately 20 million tourists, making it one of the top tourist destinations in the Middle East. However, the pandemic saw a drastic reduction in these numbers, with only 10 million tourists in 2020. By 2022, the number of tourists rebounded to 15 million, reflecting efforts to revitalize the tourism sector. This resurgence in tourism coupled with population growth has significantly increased the demand for water, stressing the existing water infrastructure and resources.

Figure 11. Population and Tourist Growth in Saudi Arabia (2010-2022)

Impact on Water Demand

The combined effect of population growth and tourist influx places considerable strain on Saudi Arabia's water resources. The increased water demand necessitates robust water management and infrastructure development to ensure a sustainable water supply. The average daily water consumption per capita in Saudi Arabia is approximately 300 liters, significantly higher than the global average of 150 liters. With a population of 35 million, this translates to a daily water demand of 10.5 billion liters, or approximately 3.8 trillion liters annually.

To put this into perspective, the annual water consumption in Saudi Arabia is comparable to the combined annual water usage of several small countries. This substantial demand underscores the critical need for effective water management strategies. The high water consumption rate can be attributed to various factors, including cultural practices, lifestyle, and the hot and arid climate that necessitates higher water use for cooling and hydration.

Strategies for Saudi Water Shortages Amid Tourism Growth

Introduction to Reverse Osmosis Technology

Saudi Arabia's water scarcity is a multifaceted issue that necessitates a comprehensive and innovative approach to secure a sustainable water supply for its population and economic activities. Reverse Osmosis (RO) technology plays a crucial role in addressing this challenge by converting seawater into potable water.

Implementation and Impact of RO Desalination

RO technology is highly efficient in removing salts and impurities from seawater (Shemer and Semiat, 2017). The Kingdom has made substantial investments in developing and expanding RO desalination infrastructure to ensure a consistent and reliable supply of potable water.

In Saudi Arabia, the daily production volume of desalinated water using RO technology varies depending on the capacity of individual plants (Tokui et al., 2014). Large-scale desalination plants, such as the Ras Al Khair and Shoaiba facilities, are capable of producing substantial quantities of water. For example, the Ras Al Khair plant alone has a capacity of producing over 1 million cubic meters (approximately 264 million gallons) of potable water per day through a combination of RO and multi-stage flash (MSF) technologies (El-Ghonemy, 2012; Tokui et al., 2014).

Figure 12. Sea Water Treatment Process Using RO

On an annual basis, Saudi Arabia is one of the largest producers of desalinated water in the world (El-Ghonemy, 2012). According to the Saline Water Conversion Corporation (SWCC), Saudi Arabia's desalination plants collectively produce over 3 million cubic meters (approximately 792 million gallons) of desalinated water per day (Council, 2021; El-Ghonemy, 2012). This equates to nearly 1.1 billion cubic meters (approximately 290 billion gallons) annually. This vast production capacity caters not only to domestic consumption but also to industrial and agricultural needs, which are critical for the country's economic development.

Figure 13: Daily and Annual Production Capacities of Desalinated Water Using RO Technology in Saudi Arabia

The reliance on desalinated water is evident in the fact that it accounts for a significant portion of the country's total water consumption. In major cities like Riyadh, Jeddah, and Dammam, desalinated water constitutes a major share of the municipal water supply. For instance, Riyadh, the capital city, depends on desalinated water transported from the coast via extensive pipeline networks.

The strategic importance of RO technology in Saudi Arabia's water management cannot be overstated. The country continues to invest in expanding its desalination capacity to keep pace with growing demand. Projects like the Jubail Desalination Plant Expansion, which aims to add several hundred thousand cubic meters per day of production capacity, highlight the

ongoing efforts to bolster water security through advanced desalination techniques.

Operational Insights into Saudi Arabia's RO Desalination

In Saudi Arabia, desalination plays a crucial role in meeting the country's freshwater demands due to its arid climate and limited freshwater resources (Husain and Khalil, 2013; Ouda, 2014b). With minimal rainfall and the majority of its land being desert, Saudi Arabia faces significant challenges in securing adequate freshwater supplies. Consequently, the country has heavily invested in desalination technologies, particularly reverse osmosis (RO), to ensure a stable and reliable water supply for its population and various industries.

Drawbacks of Reverse Osmosis Technology in Saudi Arabia

Despite its effectiveness, reverse osmosis technology presents several challenges, particularly in energy consumption, membrane fouling, contaminant removal, wastewater disposal, and sensitivity to feed water quality. Addressing these drawbacks requires significant investment in advanced technologies and infrastructure, as well as ongoing research and innovation to improve the efficiency and sustainability of RO desalination in Saudi Arabia.

High Energy Consumption

One of the primary drawbacks of RO technology is its high energy consumption. The process of forcing water through a semipermeable membrane at high pressure requires a significant amount of energy, making it costly to operate. In Saudi Arabia, desalination plants, including those using RO, are estimated to consume about 240 kWh of energy per cubic meter of water produced (El-Ghonemy, 2012). Given the country's heavy reliance on desalination, this translates to substantial energy use. For instance, the Ras Al Khair desalination plant, with its capacity of producing 1 million cubic meters of water per day, consumes around 240,000 MWh daily (El-Ghonemy, 2012), which significantly contributes to the operational costs and carbon footprint.

Membrane Fouling

Another common issue with RO systems is membrane fouling. Over time, the membranes used in the process can become fouled with impurities and contaminants, reducing their efficiency and lifespan. This necessitates frequent cleaning and maintenance, adding to the operational costs. In Saudi Arabia, where feed water from the Red Sea and the Arabian Gulf can be particularly saline and contain high levels of organic matter, the rate of membrane fouling is a significant concern. The cost of replacing or cleaning membranes can be substantial, with maintenance expenses for large-scale plants running into millions of dollars annually.

Wastewater Disposal

The brine concentrate produced as a byproduct of the RO process needs to be properly disposed of to prevent environmental harm. Improper disposal can lead to contamination of water bodies and soil, posing risks to ecosystems and human health (Dhote et al., 2012). In Saudi Arabia, the disposal of brine is a significant environmental challenge. For example, the Ras Al Khair plant produces around 1.5 million cubic meters of brine daily. Ensuring that this concentrated brine does not harm the marine environment of the Arabian Gulf requires careful management and significant infrastructure, adding to the operational challenges and costs.

Sensitivity to Feed Water Quality

The performance of RO systems can be significantly impacted by variations in feed water quality. High levels of suspended solids, organic matter, or certain chemicals in the feed water can reduce the efficiency of the system and increase maintenance requirements. In Saudi Arabia, feed water quality can vary significantly, especially with seasonal changes and human activities. This variability necessitates continuous monitoring and pre-treatment processes to maintain RO efficiency, which further increases operational complexity and costs.

Figure 14. Comparison of RO Desalination Technology in Relation to Energy Consumption

Comparative Analysis of RO Desalination: Global Perspectives

Figure 14 depicts the energy consumption (in kWh per cubic meter) for desalination using Reverse Osmosis (RO) technology across five countries: Saudi Arabia, the United States, Spain, Singapore, and China. Saudi Arabia has the highest energy consumption for desalination using RO technology among the countries listed. This indicates a significantly higher energy cost, which might be due to older technology or less efficient energy recovery systems.

Integration of Renewable Energy with RO Technology

Integrating solar energy with Reverse Osmosis (RO) technology can significantly reduce Saudi Arabia's reliance on fossil fuels for powering desalination plants. This shift not only decreases the country's carbon footprint but also helps conserve its finite fossil fuel resources. Solar-powered RO systems can operate efficiently during daylight hours when energy demand is high. By synchronizing desalination processes with solar energy availability, these systems can maximize energy use during peak sunlight, thus optimizing operational efficiency and reducing the strain on conventional energy sources. In remote areas with limited access to the electrical grid, solar-powered RO systems provide an off-

grid solution for supplying clean drinking water. This is particularly beneficial for rural communities in Saudi Arabia, where traditional infrastructure may be lacking or insufficient.

Implementing solar-powered desalination in these regions can enhance living standards, support sustainable community development, and improve resilience against water scarcity.

Figure 15. Design Scheme of RO Solar Desalination System

Source: Hajji et al., 2016

Utilizing solar energy improves the energy efficiency of RO systems by providing a renewable and sustainable power source. This can lead to significant cost savings by reducing operational expenses associated with energy consumption. Solar energy integration helps minimize the environmental impact of desalination processes, aligning with global sustainability efforts (El-Ghonemy, 2012; Kurihara, 2020). Solar-powered RO systems offer scalability options, allowing for flexible expansion to meet growing water demand. As Saudi Arabia aims to increase its desalination capacity, solar-powered systems can be easily scaled up, providing a modular and adaptable solution. This scalability ensures that future increases in water demand can be met without a corresponding rise in fossil fuel use or greenhouse gas emissions.

The use of solar energy for RO technology helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on finite fossil fuels, supporting

Saudi Arabia's sustainability goals and its commitment to renewable energy, as outlined in initiatives such as Vision 2030. By investing in solar-powered desalination, Saudi Arabia positions itself as a leader in innovative and sustainable water management solutions. Although the initial investment in solar infrastructure may be high, the long-term operational savings from reduced energy costs can be substantial. This makes solar-powered RO systems economically advantageous over time. The development and maintenance of solar-powered desalination plants can also create job opportunities, contributing to the local economy and fostering technological expertise within the country.

Integrating solar energy with RO technology presents a multifaceted solution for Saudi Arabia's water scarcity and energy challenges. By reducing fossil fuel dependence, improving energy efficiency, providing off-grid solutions for remote areas, and offering scalable and

sustainable desalination capacity, solar-powered RO systems align with the country's sustainability goals and economic interests. This strategic integration not only enhances water security but also contributes to global efforts to mitigate climate change.

Discussion

Water Supply Analysis

The water supply analysis highlights critical regional disparities in groundwater levels and desalination's role in meeting water demand. Addressing high energy consumption and environmental impacts of desalination with renewable energy integration is essential. Adaptive strategies like rainwater harvesting and advanced agricultural practices are necessary to manage the variability in rainfall and ensure sustainable water management.

Impact of Tourist Growth on Water Resources

Tourism growth positively correlates with improved water management practices, emphasizing the need for comprehensive strategies to meet increasing demand. Efficient water use practices, advanced technologies, and region-specific solutions are crucial. Integrating water sustainability into tourism development and educating tourists on conservation can enhance water resource management.

Strategies for Addressing Water Shortages Amid Tourism Growth

Reverse Osmosis (RO) technology is vital for addressing water scarcity in Saudi Arabia, but it faces challenges like high energy use and environmental concerns. Integrating renewable energy can reduce costs and environmental impact. Exploring complementary methods like rainwater harvesting and wastewater reuse can bolster water management. Continued investment in advanced technologies and innovative solutions is essential for a sustainable water future.

Conclusion

This study highlights the urgent water management challenges facing Saudi Arabia, driven by rapid population growth and expanding tourism. The significant reliance on desalination, particularly Reverse Osmosis (RO) technology, underscores its essential role in addressing water scarcity, despite the associated high energy consumption and environmental impacts. Our findings reveal regional disparities in water supply and quality, stressing the need for efficient, region-specific water management practices. The positive correlation between tourism growth and water demand emphasizes the necessity for sustainable tourism and water use strategies. Technological advancements in RO, especially when integrated with renewable energy sources like solar power, offer promising solutions to reduce operational costs and mitigate environmental impacts. Future research should focus on developing more efficient desalination technologies, enhancing renewable energy integration, and advancing water recycling and reuse systems. Strengthening regulatory frameworks and increasing public awareness are crucial for promoting water conservation and sustainable practices. By adopting these strategies, Saudi Arabia can enhance its water security, support its economic development, and achieve its Vision 2030 goals for a sustainable and resilient future.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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